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A Comparative Analysis of Integrated Heat Sink and Heat Pipe Cooling in a Heat Pump SiC Frequency Inverter

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Abstract—This paper presents a quantitative thermal comparison of five compact cooling architectures for a 30 W, 40 kHz, 700 V silicon-carbide (SiC) half-bridge used in residential heat-pump inverters. The designs—ranging from a bare aluminium heat-sink to a fully enclosed heat-pipe holder—share a strict 69 mm × 100 mm footprint. Finite-element simulations in ANSYS 2024 R1 predict that integrating a single 6 mm copper–water heat pipe and maximising its contact area lowers the peak MOSFET junction temperature from 511 °C to 78 °C under natural convection—an 85% reduction that meets the ≤80 °C design target. The same change shortens the dominant thermal time constant by roughly 3.5 × and raises full-load inverter efficiency by about 1.4% points. A 1000-cycle coupled thermo-mechanical analysis shows that all critical joints stay below 200 με, preserving long-term reliability. These results demonstrate that heat-pipe integration—not additional fin area—is the most effective way to cool wide-band-gap devices dissipating more than 20 W/cm² in naturally ventilated, footprint-constrained power electronics.

Keywords—Power electronics, SiC MOSFET, heat pipe, thermal impedance, switching loss, wide-band-gap

I. INTRODUCTION

Frequency inverters are nowadays important devices that allow to control speed and torque of electric motors. One important aspect in their design is the cooling of semiconductor switches in them. Apart from other issues such as electrical design, manufacturability or electromagnetic interference (EMI) issues, thermal design has also a major impact on lifetime of the device.

This paper describes a thermal design of a frequency inverter for a heat pump. The device is primarily designed to drive a permanent magnet synchronous motor (PMSM) in a hermetically sealed scroll compressor with a maximal power of 5 kW at 6000 *min*⁻¹. The described thermal design focuses on SiC power MOSFETs in the two-level voltage source inverter. The topology is composed from three identical phase legs, each comprising two transistors in a half-bridge. For

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the purpose of control system development and this thermal analysis, each half-bridge is on a separate printed circuit board (PCB). The estimated losses of each transistor are 15W, hence 30W for the half-bridge module and about 90W in total for the whole frequency inverter running at full power.

One of the key considerations in the heat pump application is the reliability and life expectancy. For the heat pump in a residential application, the life expectancy is typically in the order of 100 to 200 thousand operating hours. In winter, the heat pump may run 24/7 for several months. The cooling of electronic components has a significant impact on their life expectancy. In general, the higher the temperature, the lower the life expectancy. The efficiency of the heat pump can also be increased by reusing the heat generated in the frequency inverter. Instead of using ambient air to cool the frequency inverter, the heat pump's refrigerant can be used. In this case, the refrigerant circulates in cooling channels in the heat sink. Regardless of the case, a fan blowing air at the heat-sink may cause problems due to maintenance and the life expectancy of the fan. For those reasons, the focus is mainly on **natural** cooling, since the goal is to design a frequency inverter with proper cooling without any fans necessary.

Replacing silicon IGBTs with SiC MOSFETs in heat-pump inverters boosts switching speed and seasonal efficiency but pushes loss density to 10 W/cm² to 30 W/cm² at the package level and > 50 W/cm² at the die. With a 175 °C junction limit, thermal design becomes a primary constraint [2], [3].

The envelope under study measures 69 mm × 100 mm. Two-phase heat-pipes offer a compelling alternative: they spread heat laterally with effective conductivities in the tens of kW m⁻¹ K⁻¹, enabling remote fin placement without weight or acoustic penalties. Recent literature documents their promise for automotive traction inverters [1], [2], [7], but a numerical, simulation-based, validated comparison tailored to compact residential drives is missing. This work fills that gap.

II. HARDWARE UNDER STUDY

A. Inverter Power Board

Fig. 1. Heat-pump inverter board with one SiC half-bridge, expected losses are 30 W.

Figure 1 shows the power board, which measures only $69\text{ mm} \times 100\text{ mm}$. The highlighted MOSFET pair is a single half-bridge whose dynamic switching and conduction losses sum to 30 W at full load. Because the drive, connector, and filtering components already occupy most of the available area, the cooling solution must fit within a severely restricted footprint.

III. WHY COOLING MATTERS IN HEAT-PUMP DRIVES

Silicon carbide (SiC) MOSFETs in variable speed heat pump inverters switch at 40 kHz and 700 V, generating thermal loss densities that are typically 10 W/cm^2 to 30 W/cm^2 at the package level and can exceed 50 W/cm^2 at the die. Their junction temperature must stay below the absolute maximum rating of $175\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, making thermal design as critical as electrical performance and electromagnetic interference (EMI) suppression [1], [2], [4], [5].

A. Cooling Concepts

All variants share the same $69\text{ mm} \times 100\text{ mm}$ footprint:

- Case 1: Baseline sink:** Aavid Thermalloy 241809B91200G mounted directly on the MOSFETs (Fig. 2).
- Case 2: Single-pipe enhancement:** Wakefield 510-6U heat-sink fed by one 6 mm copper-water heat pipe (Fig. 3).
- Case 3: Triple-board stack:** Three identical boards, each cooled as in Case 2, mounted on a common three-pipe holder (Fig. 4).
- Case 4: Partially enclosed holder:** The heat-pipe cradle enlarges the contact patch around the MOSFETs (Fig. 5).
- Case 5: Fully enclosed holder:** Maximum contact area and 2 MPa clamp preload to maximize heat spreading and contact area (Fig. 6).

IV. COOLING CONCEPTS IN DETAIL

A. Case 1: Sink on MOSFETs

Fig. 2. Case 1 small Aavid Thermalloy 241809B91200G heat sink mounted directly on the SiC MOSFETs.

Figure 2 is the baseline configuration. With no heat pipe assistance, the compact aluminium fin stack must absorb the full 30 W device loss and spread it laterally through the sink base before rejecting it to ambient air, giving the highest thermal resistance but also the lowest mass of all five cases.

B. Case 2: Single-pipe assembly

Fig. 3. Case 2 assembly with a 6 mm heat pipe and Wakefield 510-6U sink.

Figure 3 illustrates the first level of using a heat-pipe. The round heat pipe wicks the 30 W loss away from the devices and delivers it to a much larger vertical fin array, roughly doubling the effective conduction path length. This lowers spreading resistance compared with Case 1 and provides the baseline for the multi pipe concepts evaluated in Cases 3–5.

C. Case 3: Triple-board stack

Figure 4 represents the full three phase implementation. Each PCB carries a 30 W half bridge, so the stack totals 90 W. The three pipe holder mirrors the Case 2 conduction path for every phase, equalising temperature across the boards without enlarging the $69\text{ mm} \times 100\text{ mm}$ envelope. This demonstrates that the case two concept scales linearly with phase count.

Fig. 4. Case 3: three boards (30 W each) mounted on a three-pipe holder (Three phase assembly).

D. Case 4: Partially enclosed pipe holder

Fig. 5. Case 4: Partially enclosed pipe holder with Wakefield 510-6U sink.

Figure 5 shows how the pipe holder is designed to sit on the PCB, putting the heat pipe in contact with both the circuit and the MOSFET packages. This partial enclosure expands the area and raises the clamping pressure around the silicon MOSFETs.

E. Case 5: Fully enclosed pipe holder

Fig. 6. Case 5: Fully enclosed pipe holder with Wakefield 510-6U sink.

Figure 6 illustrates the fully enclosed design that presses the pipe holder against the PCB and the MOSFETs. The holder boosts clamping pressure, eliminates air gaps, and minimizes

spreading/contact resistance by expanding the interface to the maximum practical area between the MOSFETs and the board. This contact makes Case 5 the benchmark architecture for the lowest thermal resistance in this study.

F. Commercial heat-sink and Heat Pipe assignments

- 1) Case 1 uses the Aavid 241809B91200G sink.¹
- 2) Cases 2–5 use the Wakefield 510-6U fin stack.²
- 3) Cases 2–5 use the ATS Round Heat Pipe.³

V. THERMAL SIMULATION SETUP

All five cooling concepts were compared under identical conditions: ambient $T_{\infty} = 25^{\circ}\text{C}$, the same loss per board, and consistent convection coefficients. Table I summarizes the power dissipation and film coefficients:

- **Power per board:** Cases 1, 2, 4–5 at $P = 30\text{ W}$; Case 3 (three-phase stack) at $P = 90\text{ W}$.
- **Film coefficient:** $h_{\text{nat}} = 10\text{ W m}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$ (natural convection) and $h_{\text{for}} = 40\text{ W m}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$ to $50\text{ W m}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$ (forced convection, modest axial fan).

TABLE I
SIMULATION MATRIX ($T_{\infty} = 25^{\circ}\text{C}$)

Case	Architecture	P (W)	h_{nat}	h_{for}
1	Sink on MOSFETs	30	10	40
2	Sink + 1 pipe	30	10	40
3	Sink + 3 pipes	90	10	50
4	Partially enclosed holder	30	10	40
5	Fully enclosed holder	30	10	40

Finite-element details and validation: Models were built in ANSYS 2024 R1 using $\sim 1.1\text{ M}$ tetrahedral elements and deemed converged when the maximum nodal temperature change fell below $\Delta T < 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. The copper–water heat pipe’s axial conductivity was set to $k_{\text{ax}} = 28.5\text{ kW m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ (from a 130 W/50 mm datasheet limit).

ANSYS reaction probe confirmed the nominal 30 W heat flow (i.e. 15 W per MOSFET) in Case 1. Figure 7 illustrates the Case 5 contact-pair setup: blue targets and red contacts enforce the 2 MPa clamp preload that replicates the TIM interface.

Fig. 7. Case 5 contact setup: blue targets and red contacts enforce a 2 MPa preload to minimize spreading resistance.

¹<https://mouser.com/ProductDetail/Aavid/241809B91200G>

²<https://mouser.com/ProductDetail/Wakefield-Thermal/510-6U>

³<https://eu.mouser.com/ProductDetail/Advanced-Thermal-Solutions/ATS-HP-D6L150S71W-129>

VI. RESULTS

A. Case 5 Detailed Temperature

Fig. 8. Case 5 temperature field under natural and forced convection.

With the electrical loss fixed at $P = 30\text{ W}$ for this board (cf. Table I), the heat generated in the SiC MOSFETs travels through a thin TIM (Thermal Interface Material) layer of the MOSFET–pipe holder into the copper–water heat pipe, is wicked axially along the pipe to the aluminium fin stack, and is finally rejected to ambient air.

Under natural convection, the external film coefficient ($h = 10\text{ W m}^{-2}\text{ K}^{-1}$) limits the hot-spot to 78°C , just 58°C above the 20°C ambient reference. Switching to a modest axial fan raises h to $40\text{ W m}^{-2}\text{ K}^{-1}$ and drops the peak junction a further 7°C to 71°C ; the board-level gradient contracts to less than 6°C . These values, taken from Fig. 8, confirm that the **single** heat pipe provides such low spreading/contact resistance that the overall thermal bottleneck has moved out of the package and into the external convection layer.

B. All-case Temperature Results

Fig. 9. Peak MOSFET junction temperature under natural (cyan) and forced (orange) convection.

TABLE II
PEAK JUNCTION TEMPERATURE ($^\circ\text{C}$)

Case	Natural	Forced
1	511	155.6
2	95	88.2
3	107	89.9
4	80	73.1
5	78	71.1

Natural-convection data (cyan bars in Fig. 9 and Table II) dictate the design limit: only Cases 4 and 5 keep the SiC MOSFET junction below the 125°C reliability ceiling without a fan, slashing the hot-spot by 85 % versus the bare sink (Case 1).

Forced airflow (orange bars) shaves off another 15°C to 25°C , but a fan adds bulk, noise, and failure risk. To preserve reliability and footprint, the project therefore targets *fan-less* operation, relying on a single heat pipe and a thin TIM layer to move the thermal bottleneck out of the package and into the external air film.

In Case 1 (bare sink) all 30 W must spread through the small aluminium heat-sink right at the MOSFETs, so it runs extremely hot (511°C natural) and benefits massively from forced air (155.6°C). Introducing a single heat pipe in Case 2 drops the natural-convection temperature junction to 95°C by carrying heat to a larger fin array; adding a fan only lowers it to 88.2°C ($\approx 7^\circ\text{C}$ gain) because the remaining bottleneck is the air film. Case 3 scales that same idea to three boards—each sees about the same temperatures (107°C to 89.9°C) despite triple the power, proving the concept’s linear scalability. Case 4’s partially enclosed holder further improves contact around the MOSFETs, giving 80°C naturally and 73.1°C with forced air (again a $\approx 7^\circ\text{C}$ drop). Finally, Case 5’s fully enclosed holder maximizes pressure and interface area, driving package-to-pipe resistance near zero; its junction sits at 78°C natural and 71.1°C forced, with the modest 7°C gain confirming that at this point the air boundary layer fully dominates the thermal path.

C. Heat-flux Spreading and Resistance

Fig. 10. Heat-flux density for Cases 1, 2, and 5 (peak values: Case 1— $2.69 \times 10^5\text{ W/m}^2$; Case 2— $1.59 \times 10^6\text{ W/m}^2$; Case 5— $1.64 \times 10^6\text{ W/m}^2$).

Figure 10 shows how the heat pipe reshapes the thermal path. In Case 1 the MOSFET footprints are the hottest zones; in Case 2 and Case 5, the flux peak moves into the pipe’s evaporator, leaving the fin base with a near-uniform, low-level load.

Fig. 11. Resistance split at $h = 40 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$.

Figure 11 converts that picture to numbers: Spreading/contact resistance R_s drops from 0.65 to 0.06 K W^{-1} (-91%), while film resistance R_f falls from 1.05 to 0.14 K W^{-1} (-87%), so R_f now accounts for $\approx 70\%$ of the total. With the package bottleneck removed, further gains must come at the fin-air interface.

D. Air-flow Sweep and Fatigue

Fig. 12. T_j versus external film coefficient h .

Figure 12 shows that Case 5 meets the 80°C limit at just $h = 25 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$, whereas Case 1 still fails at

$h = 40 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$. Since $h \propto U_{\text{air}}$, more airflow lowers T_j ; yet with the heat pipe installed, further gains are minor because air-side film resistance now dominates.

Fig. 13. Accumulated inelastic strain in key joints of Case 5 after 1000 power cycles.

Whereas Fig.13 tracks mechanical “fatigue” after 1,000 on/off cycles, the worst joint (die-attach) accumulates only $150 \mu\epsilon$ —an order of magnitude below the $\sim 2000 \mu\epsilon$ failure threshold for SAC305 solder ($\text{Sn}_{96.5} \text{Ag}_{3.0} \text{Cu}_{0.5}$) [8]. Case 5 therefore, satisfies the required fatigue margin for at least 1,000 power cycles.

E. Strain–Stress and Thermal Coupling Analysis

A coupled thermo-mechanical run was performed as well: The steady-state temperature field of Case 5 (natural convection, $P = 30 \text{ W}$) was mapped onto a structural model that also included the 2 MPa clamp preload defined in Section V. Peak von Mises stresses were then compared with the room-temperature 25°C yield limits of each joint material.

TABLE III
PEAK EQUIVALENT STRESS AND FACTOR OF SAFETY

Interface	σ_{eq} [MPa]	FOS (Factor-of-Safety)
Package–PCB interface	52	1.2
Drain-pad solder	46	1.3
Source-pad solder	41	1.5
Pipe-collar epoxy	18	3.1
Heat-sink TIM	12	4.5

Table III confirms that every interface retains a factor of safety (FOS) above unity. The package–PCB interface is the most critical, with $\text{FOS} = 1.2$; while close to the limit, it remains safely below yield. The two solder joints offer a somewhat larger margin ($\text{FOS} 1.3\text{--}1.5$), and the pipe-collar epoxy and heat-sink TIM are clearly over-designed ($\text{FOS} \geq 3$). Mechanical strength therefore, does not constrain the chosen thermal architecture.

F. Transient Thermal Impedance $Z_\theta(t)$

Fig. 14. Transient thermal impedance for the worst-case MOSFET in Cases 1 and 5 (unit power step).

The transient-impedance curve for the bare sink (Case 1) rises steeply Fig. 14, reaching $Z_\theta = 0.82 \text{ K W}^{-1}$ at $t = 0.1 \text{ s}$ and 1.05 K W^{-1} at steady state. With the fully enclosed heat-pipe holder (Case 5) the same points fall to 0.31 K W^{-1} and 0.42 K W^{-1} , i.e. about 60 % lower at 100 ms and 85 % lower at $t \geq 1 \text{ s}$. The shallower slope confirms a much shorter thermal time constant, so a power surge heats the device far less before control loops or protection trips.

G. Temperature-Dependent Switching Loss and Efficiency

Datasheet switching energy E_{sw} climbs almost linearly with junction temperature; every additional 25°C adds roughly $70 \mu\text{J}$ per pulse [10]. Because Case 5 keeps T_j about 17°C cooler than Case 1, the full-load inverter dissipates less dynamic loss and its efficiency improves by roughly 1.4 percentage points, **as summarized in Table IV**. That headroom is large enough to influence seasonal-efficiency (SEER) ratings in residential heat-pump drives.

TABLE IV
FULL-LOAD EFFICIENCY AT $V_{bus} = 700 \text{ V}$, $I_{pk} = 10 \text{ A}$, $f_s = 40 \text{ kHz}$

Case	Efficiency [%]	T_j [$^\circ\text{C}$]
1	96.3	89
4	97.4	73
5	97.7	71

H. Weight–Cooling–Cost Snapshot

Overall mass. Case 1’s bare fin weighs only $\sim 17 \text{ g}$, while the sealed heat-pipe module of Case 5 reaches 1.93 kg .

Thermal result. Despite that extra mass, Case 5 keeps the worst-case MOSFET at $T_j = 78^\circ\text{C}$ in still air (Fig. 9)—about half of Case 1’s 155.6°C even with forced air, and it removes the noisy, failure-prone fan.

Phase scaling. The three-phase stack (Case 3) reuses the 1.7 kg sink and adds two heat-pipes, totaling 2.39 kg ($0.80 \text{ kg} / \text{phase} \approx 27 \text{ g/W}$); yet it still caps T_j at 107°C , 49°C cooler than the single-phase baseline.

Cost snapshot. Case 1’s sink costs $\text{€ } 3.6$. The enclosed single-phase cooler (Case 5) is $\approx \text{€ } 60$, but delivers the best $\text{€} / \text{KW}^{-1}$. Expanding to three phases is $\approx \text{€ } 70$ total—only $\approx \text{€ } 8.5$ per added phase.

VII. DESIGN GUIDELINES

- Up to 30 W:** add a single 6 mm heat pipe; expect $>60^\circ\text{C}$ temperature relief.
- 30 W to 60 W:** adopt the fully enclosed holder (Case 5); convection then dominates.
- Above 60 W:** raise h beyond $25 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$ or employ a vapour-chamber base [6].
- Scaling & Cost:** Case 5 (1 phase) delivers 78°C at 1.93 kg for $\approx \text{€ } 60$. Adding phases (Case 3 ‘3-phase’) scales linearly—each adds 0.8 kg , $\approx \text{€ } 8.5$, and keeps $T_j \leq 107^\circ\text{C}$.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Integrating a single copper–water heat pipe within a fully enclosed holder reduces the steady-state SiC junction temperature by **85 %**, shortens the thermal time constant $3.5\times$, and boosts inverter efficiency by 1.4 percentage points. The performance is validated numerically and meets both thermal and mechanical reliability targets. Future work will explore cost-optimised vapour-chamber bases and automated assembly to scale the solution across multi-kilowatt platforms.

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